

Proton-Assisted Air Oxidation Mechanisms of Iron(II) bis-Thiosemicarbazone Complexes at Physiological pH: a Kinetic-Mechanistic Study

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ABSTRACT

The kinetics of oxidation for different biologically-active Fe^{II} *bis*-thiosemicarbazone complexes in water at varying dioxygen concentration, temperature, pressure, and pH has been monitored. The oxidation reactions observed can be resolved as a single-step process, producing the expected ferric complex, with rates increasing with decreasing pH. From the pH-dependence of the observed rate constants, a rate law with two terms can be derived, one of them being independent of the acid concentration and the other one showing a saturation behaviour with respect to [H⁺]. Those results indicate the existence of two parallel pathways for oxidation; the acid-independent pathway is only operative for the complexes with ligands bearing terminal, non-coordinated, unsubstituted amines, whereas the term with a [H⁺]-limiting kinetic behaviour is observed for all the complexes and indicates that the reacting species has to be protonated prior to the oxidation step. From the data collected, the rate law and the thermal and pressure activation parameters have been used to interpret the operating reaction mechanisms. DFT calculations have been also carried out in order to explain the empirical trends, **and the results suggest the possibility of formation under steady-state conditions of Fe^{III} superoxo and hydroperoxo intermediates.** The kinetics of reaction with hydrogen peroxide has been also studied and it was found to show a complex behaviour, involving a variety of processes, which include ligand oxidation to semicarbazones and photochemical reactions (both on the ferrous and ferric complexes). When the illumination of the sample is limited to wavelengths within the 500-800 nm range, a simpler reactivity pattern is observed. It is clear that a rather complex combination of different mechanisms are actuating for the oxidation reaction with hydrogen peroxide.

INTRODUCTION

By the end of the previous century iron-chelation therapy emerged as an effective strategy in the treatment of iron overload, an abnormal accumulation of Fe in the body that ultimately leads to organ damage.¹⁻³ This is believed to happen *via* oxidative stress caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as the highly oxidizing hydroxyl radical ($\bullet\text{OH}$), as a result of Fenton-type processes.⁴ The aim of iron chelation is, consequently, to regulate Fe concentrations through metal sequestration. More recently, some iron chelators have been proved to inhibit the iron-dependent enzyme Ribonucleotide Reductase (RR), which catalyses the formation of the deoxynucleoside triphosphate DNA building block. The RR enzyme presents a higher expression in many types of cancers, and thus its inhibition has been explored in anti-cancer therapy;⁵ redox-active iron-chelators have been used for this purpose.

Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) are a class of metal chelators that can bind several metals with versatile coordination environments.^{6,7} From a pharmacological perspective, they are of particular interest due to their biological properties, which range from antimalarian,⁸ to antibacterial and antifungal.⁹ Furthermore, many TSCs have shown promising results in relation to antiproliferative activity and intracellular iron mobilization.^{10,11} Current research is focused in designing new generations of TSCs based on the chemical and biological information that is already known. Taking this background into account, understanding the solution behaviour of TSCs and their iron complexes under biologically relevant conditions, in particular in oxidation processes, is fundamental and expected to lead to the design of more efficient systems.

Previous kinetic-mechanistic studies on iron *bis*-thiosemicarbazone complexes have concluded that outer-sphere interactions are determinant for the trends in the reaction rates obtained. For instance, the reaction of the oxidised $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{TSC})_2]^+$ derivatives with oxyhaemoglobin has been examined, and the involvement of hydrogen-bonding outer-sphere interactions has been found the keystone of the reactivity.^{12,13} Furthermore, the presence of $\text{NH}\cdots\text{O}_2$ interactions for $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TSC})_2]$ complexes with TSCs bearing unsubstituted amine groups in MeOH solution has been established during oxidation reaction.¹⁴ Recently, these interactions have also been found relevant in different systems involving M-O₂ coordination¹⁵ and N₂ activation;¹⁶ even very strong hydrogen bond interactions have been held responsible for electron delocalization in metal clusters.¹⁷ In fact, hydrogen bonding interactions have also been involved in multiple-site concerted proton-electron transfer (MS-PCET) reactions¹⁸ and spin crossover (SCO) phenomena in complexes featuring

coordinated oxygen.¹⁹

Ferrous and ferric complexes of these thiosemicarbazone ligands have been characterised as low spin hexacoordinate, showing high stability even in the presence of EDTA and DFO at fairly acidic pH.¹⁵ Nevertheless, in order to study their oxidation by O₂ in aqueous solution, alternative approaches have to be employed. Simple coordination of dioxygen to the metal to give heptacoordinate iron centres has to be considered.²⁰⁻²² Even partial dechelation of the TSC ligands to produce an hexacoordinate complex with an iron-O₂ bond can act as a starting point for the oxidation reaction, as found for haeme derivatives, is feasible.²³

Here we present a kinetic-mechanistic study of the reaction of three [Fe^{II}(TSC)₂] complexes with dioxygen and hydrogen peroxide at physiological pH. Namely, the Fe complexes that were examined feature two TSCs of the di-2-pyridylketone family (DpT series), and one of the 2-benzoylpyridine family (BpT series), Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The thiosemicarbazones of the di-2-pyridylketone (HDpT, HDp44mT) and 2-benzoylpyridine families (HBpT), along with their Fe^{II} complexes, were prepared and characterized as described in the literature.^{24,25} Hydrogen peroxide solutions were prepared by using commercial 30% (w/w) stabilized aqueous H₂O₂ solutions, and the final concentrations were determined using well-documented methods.²⁶ All other reagents were commercially available and used as received.

Buffer solutions were prepared as described in the literature.²⁷ Typically, they were 15 mM of MOPS or MES in aqueous solution, an ionic strength of 100 mM (adjusted with NaClO₄), and a pH range from 5.0 to 8.0.

Instruments

The UV-Vis time-resolved spectral changes were recorded using CARY 50, HP 8452A or Agilent 8453 instruments with a thermostated multicell transport. Measurements at varying pressure were registered with a J&M Tidas spectrophotometer connected to a purpose-built pressurizing system, where samples were confined inside a pill-box cell; the system and its elements have been previously described.²⁸ Cyclic voltammograms were collected using a Biologic SP-150 potentiostat using 1.0 mM of the ferric complexes dissolved in a MeCN/H₂O (70/30) mixture containing 100 mM of TBAP (tetrabutylammonium perchlorate) as the supporting electrolyte. Glassy carbon was used as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl/sat. KCl, as the reference electrode and a Pt wire as the auxiliary electrode; the scan rate was fixed usually at 20 mV/s and solutions were purged with N₂. All electrochemical data indicated is referenced *versus* NHE. Mass spectra were performed at the Unitat d'Espectrometria de Masses (Universitat de Barcelona) in a LC/MSD-TOF.

Kinetics

Fresh and air-free stock solutions of the ferrous thiosemicarbazone complexes were prepared using standard Schlenk techniques in methanol.²⁹ Buffer solutions were prepared as indicated above and were deaerated with N₂; 4% of degassed MeOH was also added to insure the iron complex solubility. Air-saturation of the buffer solutions was achieved by stirring thermostated open beakers, at each working temperature (10, 15, 25, and 35 °C), for 20 minutes. For the oxidation reactions by

dioxygen, different ratios of air-saturated and deaerated solutions were added to a thermostated 1 cm quartz cuvette to achieve the dioxygen concentrations desired. The actual concentrations, generally between $(4-26)\times 10^{-2}$ mM, were calculated considering that the solubility of O_2 at a given temperature corresponds to its concentration in the air-saturated solutions. Ferrous complex stock solutions were added to obtain a final concentration of $(5-10)\times 10^{-3}$ mM in the cell, with the methanol concentration kept at the 4-5 % range; these were then sealed with rubber septa. For the oxidations with hydrogen peroxide, the samples were deaerated as indicated above, and different amounts of H_2O_2 (to a final concentration within the $(0.5-18)\times 10^{-1}$ mM range) were added in the UV-Vis cells.

The time-resolved spectral changes were typically monitored in the 200-800 nm region when using dioxygen as the oxidant, whereas reactions with hydrogen peroxide were monitored either from 200-800 or 500-800 nm, depending on the runs. The observed rate constants were generally quantified at the MLCT maximum of *ca.* 620 nm by fitting the time-resolved data with the SPECFIT³⁰ or Reactlab Kinetics³¹ software packages. Results of the dioxygen reactions were fitted by using an A→B single exponential model. An additional B→C exponential was used when a slow drift appeared by the end of the spectral changes, which was disregarded given the lack of reproducibility in its concentration dependence.¹⁴ For reactions with hydrogen peroxide showing non exponential kinetic traces at 620 nm, the initial rate of the reaction (v_{init}), taken as the initial slope of the Absorbance *versus* time plots, and its dependence with pH and reactant concentrations was studied. Table S1 collects all the values of the derived k_{obs} under the conditions studied.

Computational methods

DFT calculations were carried out with Gaussian 09 Rev. D.01.³² Geometry optimisations employed the BP86 functional^{33,34} and were performed including the effect of the water solvent via the SMD approach.³⁵ SDD effective core potentials³⁶ and associated basis sets were used to represent Fe and S centres, with added d-orbital polarisation ($\zeta = 0.503$)³⁷ on the latter. Pople style 6-31G(d,p) basis sets^{38,39} were used for all other atoms. An ultrafine grid corresponding to 99 radial shells and 590 angular points was employed for the numerical integration of the density. Minima and transition state geometries were confirmed as such through analytical frequency calculations, having zero and one imaginary frequencies, respectively. These calculations were also employed to obtain the thermal and entropic contributions to the Gibbs energy, evaluated at 298.15 K and 1 atm. IRC calculations and subsequent optimizations were performed to confirm the minima either side of the relevant transition-states.^{40,41}

The electronic energies of the previously optimized geometries were re-computed using the same BP86 functional and the triple-zeta cc-pVTZ basis set for all atoms,⁴² also including solvent effects self-consistently via the SMD approach. The free energies reported in the main text are based on these improved electronic energies, together with the corresponding free energy correction obtained at the optimization level, and Grimme's D3 correction for dispersion effects (with the Becke-Johnson damping function).^{43,44} For the DpT complex, additional test calculations were conducted with B3LYP-D3BJ, M06-D3, PBE0-D3BJ and B97D functionals via single point energy calculations on the BP86-optimized species. These results are included in the Supporting Information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reactions with dioxygen

The oxidation reactions of the Fe^{II} bis-TSC complexes by dioxygen were monitored using time-resolved UV-Vis spectroscopy in aqueous solution at buffered pH (see Figure 1). All experiments were run using variable dioxygen concentrations ($(0.38\text{-}2.6)\times 10^{-4}$ M) and temperatures (10-35 °C) under pseudo first order conditions ($[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TSC})] = (1\text{-}0.5)\times 10^{-5}$ M).

Figure 1.- Absorbance/time spectral changes observed during the oxidation of an air saturated 0.01 mM $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{Dp44mT})_2]$ aqueous solution ($[\text{MOPS}] = 15\text{mM}$, $I_{(\text{NaClO}_4)} = 100\text{ mM}$, 4-5 % of added MeOH) at pH = 7.1 and $T = 25\text{ °C}$.

For all the complexes studied, the fitting of the data according to that indicated in the Experimental section produced a pseudo first order rate constant (k_{obs}), which shows a linear dependence with dioxygen concentrations for all the range of pH used (Figure 2a), indicating that the rate law is $k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{ox}} \times [\text{O}_2]$. Table S2 collects all the second order rate constants, k_{ox} , determined as a function of the temperature and acidity.⁴⁵ The pH dependence of the observed rate constants, depicted in Figure 2a, clearly indicates a decrease of k_{ox} on increasing pH, and Figure 2b shows the saturation behaviour observed for k_{ox} on the value of $[\text{H}^+]$. The plots were consequently fitted to a saturation by protonation rate law, as shown in Equation 1, and the values of the kinetic parameters derived for the different systems at 25 °C are collected in Table 1.

Figure 2.- a) Plot of the dependence of the observed pseudo-first order rate constants with dioxygen concentrations at varying pH for the complex $[Fe^{II}(Dp44mT)_2]$ at 25 °C. b) Plot of the $[H^+]$ -dependence of the second order rate constants (k_{ox}) for the oxidation of the Fe^{II} bis-thiosemicarbazone complexes studied at 25 °C (fitted lines correspond to Equation 1).

$$k_{ox} = {}^0k_{ox} + \frac{{}^Hk_{ox} \text{app}K_H[H^+]}{1 + \text{app}K_H[H^+]}$$

Equation 1

Table 1.- Summary of the kinetic (298 K) and thermal and pressure activation parameters determined for the systems indicated in aqueous solution (15 mM MOPS buffer,^a 100 mM NaClO₄). Electrochemical data (*versus* NHE) are also included for further discussion.^[31]

TSC	$E^0(Fe^{III/II})$ /mV	${}^0k_{ox}$ /s ⁻¹ M ⁻¹	${}^Hk_{ox}$ /s ⁻¹ M ⁻¹	$\text{app}K_H$ /10 ⁶ M ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger_0 /kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger_0 /J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔV^\ddagger_0 ^b /cm ³ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger_H /kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger_H /J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔV^\ddagger_H ^c /cm ³ mol ⁻¹
HDp44mT	+166	~0	77±15	0.9±0.3	--	--	--	96±7	110±20	+8.2±0.5
HDpT	+165	1.5±0.1	11±1	1.9±0.5	75±2	9±8	-2.9±0.6	58±4	-32±14	-12±1
HBpT	+120	4.5±0.5	23±3	2.5±0.8	63±5	-22±17	n.d.	55±1	-36±5	n.d.

^a pH = 5.0 MES buffer. ^b pH = 8.0 at 283 K. ^c pH = 5.0 at 283 K. n.d.: Not determined

The experimental rate law can be interpreted according to a mechanism in which two parallel

pathways coexist (${}^0k_{\text{ox}}$ and ${}^{\text{H}}k_{\text{ox}}$). The acid independent ${}^0k_{\text{ox}}$ term in Equation 1 corresponds to direct oxidation of the iron complex with O_2 , while the limiting acid-dependent term corresponds to an apparent protonation process (${}^{\text{app}}K_{\text{H}}$) leading to a rate-determining oxidation of the protonated species (${}^{\text{H}}k_{\text{ox}}$). Given that a single kinetic step was observed for all the systems studied (see Figure 1), and that the final spectra correspond to the fully characterised ferric species, a rate-determining one electron oxidation with formation of $\text{O}_2^{\cdot -}$, or its protonated HO_2 form, can be thought to operate for both pathways.

Scheme 2 summarises the reaction sequence proposed, where $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$ and $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]$ stand for any protonated form of the iron complexes. Following the initial oxidation, the reaction is completed by subsequent fast steps involving the transient formation of H_2O_2 and OH^{\cdot} radicals that lead to the oxidation of three additional equivalents of iron complex, as proposed in literature for the oxidation of other coordinatively saturated metal complexes.^{46,47} Hydrogen peroxide is not detected during these air-oxidation reactions,⁴⁸ indicating that the rates of complex oxidation by H_2O_2 are effectively faster than those of its production, a point that has been confirmed when reacting the $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TSC})_2]$ complexes with H_2O_2 (see next section). Additional processes as superoxide dismutation^{49,50} and protonation^{51,52} are also expected to occur under the experimental conditions used in the kinetic studies, although they are faster than the initial oxidation with dioxygen.^{22,53}

Scheme 2

The stoichiometric consideration indicated in the previous paragraph makes the real value of $k_{\text{obs}}(\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}+\text{O}_2) = k_{\text{obs}}/4$ and that of $k_{\text{ox}}(\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}+\text{O}_2) = k_{\text{ox}}/4$. Nevertheless, the differences do not affect the general comparative trends indicated in Table 1 for ${}^0k_{\text{ox}}$ and ${}^{\text{H}}k_{\text{ox}}$, which should be considered as the apparent experimental data. Furthermore, the values of ${}^{\text{app}}K_{\text{H}}$ and ΔH^\ddagger and ΔV^\ddagger are unaffected, and ΔS^\ddagger will be $\ln(4)$ lower ($1.4 \text{ J K}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$), which is within the experimental error of the values determined.

A similar reaction scheme has been reported for the O_2 oxidation of Fe^{II} complexes with EDTA and related ligands.²⁰⁻²² In these complexes the existing water ligand in a seventh coordination position is initially substituted by O_2 , both by spontaneous and acid-catalysed processes, to produce $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{L}(\text{O}_2)]$ and $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL})(\text{O}_2)]$, and then both species undergo inner-sphere electron transfer to yield Fe^{III} and superoxide. However, this kind of inner-sphere process seems unlikely in our case for the ${}^0k_{\text{ox}}$ pathway due to the fact that both ferrous and ferric *bis*-thiosemicarbazone complexes are hexacoordinate with very similar structures and bond lengths due to the rigidity of the *bis*-tridentate arrangement, thus facilitating outer-sphere processes.^{24,25} Nevertheless, in such case there should be a correlation between the ${}^0k_{\text{ox}}$ values and the oxidation potential of the iron complexes, and the values in Table 1 for the HDp44mT and HDpT complexes are dramatically diverse (${}^0k_{\text{ox}} \approx 0$ for the Dp44mT complex) despite their similar oxidation potentials. Therefore, the acid-independent pathway somehow requires the interaction of O_2 with the iron centre. In principle, this could be envisaged to take place *via* the formation of a seven-coordinate intermediate or the partial dechelation of the thiosemicarbazone ligand to keep the six-coordinate geometry. Although both processes are unprecedented for this kind of complexes, the presence of such intermediates in steady-state conditions cannot be underestimated.

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were at this point employed to study the possible ways in which O_2 can bind to the three $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TSC})_2]$ complexes studied. For simplicity, herein we will focus on the results obtained for the DpT complex (see SI for the BpT and Dp44mT analogues). Computations started with the optimization of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{DpT})_2]$ in its singlet, triplet, and quintet states. As expected,⁵⁴ the singlet state was found to be lowest in energy, with triplet and quintet states being higher in free energy by 20.6 and 28.3 kcal/mol, respectively. Subsequently, the possible

formation of seven-coordinate $[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})_2(\text{O}_2)]$ species resulting from the coordination of an external O_2 molecule was studied; despite multiple attempts no such species could be optimised. Instead, the calculations led to either the release of the O_2 ligand (regenerating the initial $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{DpT})_2]$ species) or to the opening of one of the chelate rings *via* the cleavage of a Fe–S bond, thus resulting in the formation of new triplet six-coordinate species. The latter structure, labelled as ${}^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}_{\text{s}})\text{O}_2]$ in Figure 3, was computed to be 20.5 kcal/mol above the separated reactants, and the O–O distance of 1.31 Å is compatible with its formulation as a Fe^{III} -superoxo complex. In addition, the transition state for its formation, ${}^3\text{TS1}$, was also found at a relative free energy of 31.6 kcal/mol. Interestingly, the latter can be described as seven-coordinate, as it features a contact between the iron centre and the incoming O_2 ($d(\text{Fe}-\text{O}) = 2.50$ Å), as well as an elongated $\text{Fe}\cdots\text{S}$ distance of 3.07 Å associated with the opening of the chelate ring.

Comentado [D1]: Lo de singulete me parece lioso.

Figure 3. Computational (DFT) results on the reaction between $[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})_2]$ and O_2 to form ${}^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}_{\text{s}})\text{O}_2]$. Values in italics correspond to relative free energies in kcal/mol, distances given in Å.

Comentado [D2]: Singulete???

These computations are compatible with ${}^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}_{\text{s}})\text{O}_2]$ being a species formed under steady-state conditions for the spontaneous path indicated in Scheme 2. Unfortunately, analogous computations on the Dp44mT complex only result in minimal energetic and structural changes, therefore not explaining the lack of such pathway for the latter. Evidently, the different degree of substitution at the dangling amine group of the TSC ligands must be responsible for this difference. Indeed, while the intermediates from the DpT and BpT complexes could *a priori* undergo an intramolecular proton transfer that would result in the formation of a –OOH ligand (followed by a

protonation by the solvent), such possibility is not available at the N-methylated Dp44mT counterpart.

As for the acid-catalysed path, protonation of the dangling pyridine in DpT and Dp44mT complexes can be ruled out because all three species show close values of $^{app}K_H$, despite the absence of a dangling pyridine in the BpT ligand. In fact, pyridine protonation on free HDpT and HDp44mT ligands occurs with $\log K_H$ values close to 4,²⁵ the values in the complexes being probably lower, so that protonation of this group is expected to occur at pH values much lower than those used in this work. Furthermore, the values of $^{app}K_H$ in Table 1 produce $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TSC})_2\text{H}]^+ / [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{TSC})_2]$ concentration ratios within the 0.02-0.06 range at pH=7.7 (0.55-1.5 at pH=6.3), which indicate that the amounts of protonated complexes under the experimental conditions used are significant. Nevertheless, the lack of noticeable changes in the spectra of the complexes at different pH values indicates that complex protonation does not lead to partial dechelation of the ligand. This leaves the uncoordinated $-\text{N}(\text{Me})_2$ (or $-\text{NH}_2$), or the central nitrogen of the $\cdot\cdot\text{S}-\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{N}\cdot\cdot$ chelate group, present in all three complexes, as the most likely protonation sites. DFT computations on the relative stability of these isomers show that protonation of the central nitrogen at one of the DpT ligands, producing a $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{\text{SC}^{\text{NHN}}})]^+$ species, is favoured over protonation on the dangling amine, $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{\text{NH}})]^+$, by 14.7 kcal/mol (see Figure 4).⁵⁵ **This finding is in agreement with previous reports showing that Fe^{II} complexes of related TSCs exist in aqueous solution in two forms, protonated and deprotonated, the protonated form containing the proton at the central nitrogen and the value of $\log K_H$ for protonation being close to 6. Although in those cases protonation is signalled by a shift of 20-80 nm in the absorption band, complete protonation is only achieved at pH lower than those used in the present work, so that the absence of such shifts in the present cases is probably caused by a combination of smaller shifts and incomplete conversion to the protonated complex.**

As found for the acid-independent path, sulfur dechelation by O_2 coordination at these protonated species also represents the most likely starting point of the oxidation process in acidic conditions. This reaction has been computed for both isomers and the results are also included in Figure 4. Focussing on the most stable $[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{\text{SC}^{\text{NHN}}})]^+$ species, it is found that the formation of $^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{\text{SC}^{\text{NHN}}})\text{O}_2]^+$, with a $d(\text{O}-\text{O}) = 1.31 \text{ \AA}$ again compatible with a Fe^{III} -superoxo complex, is endergonic by 18.4 kcal/mol (*cf.* 20.5 kcal/mol for $^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{\text{S}})\text{O}_2]$), and takes place with a free energy barrier of 31.8 kcal/mol (*cf.* 31.9 kcal/mol for $^3\text{T}1$). In fact, neither the protonation site nor the neutral or protonated state of the complex seems to lead to major effects on the computed

Comentado [D3]: Singlete??

Comentado [D4]: Singlete??

Comentado [M5]: Refs

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kinetics and thermodynamics of the process.

Figure 4. Computational (DFT) results on the possible isomers of $[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^H)]^+$ and their reaction with O_2 . Values in italics correspond to relative free energies in kcal/mol, distances given in Å.

Comentado [D6]: Sin singletes??
No deberian ser TS2 y TS3???

Interestingly, it has been only possible to compute a reasonable mechanism for the following steps of the acid dependent oxidation pathway from the less stable ${}^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{NH_s})\text{O}_2]^+$ species, which can undergo a proton transfer that leads to the hydroperoxo species ${}^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}_s)(\text{O}_2\text{H})]^+$, as shown in Figure 5. Energetically, the process is only exergonic by 2.0 kcal/mol, therefore indicating that both structures roughly feature the same relative stability. Regarding the associated transition state, ${}^3\text{TS4}$, it appears at +36.1 kcal/mol in the free energy profile and features an intermediate $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}\cdots\text{N}$ interaction associated with the intramolecular H^+ transfer. Comparison of the $\text{O}-\text{O}$ distances between ${}^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{NH_s})\text{O}_2]^+$ and ${}^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}_s)(\text{O}_2\text{H})]^+$ show the expected elongation of the bond from 1.308 Å to 1.469 Å. Nevertheless, it is also worth noting that the transferred proton in ${}^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}_s)(\text{O}_2\text{H})]^+$ is not in the proximities of the central nitrogen of the $\cdots\text{S}-\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{N}\cdots$

Comentado [D7]: Mejor, para evitar lo de abajo?

Comentado [D8]: El 4 no??

chelate group, as the computations show that in such case a barrierless proton transfer would lead to the formation of $^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{\text{SCNHN}})_2\text{O}_2]^+$ (note that such species is 7.8 kcal/mol more stable than $^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}_s)(\text{O}_2\text{H})]^+$). Unlike the neutral pathway, such proton assisted mechanism in Figure 5 is not dependent on the degree of substitution at the dangling amine group of the TSC ligands, and therefore it will be available for the three studied metal complexes. Indeed, additional computations on the Dp44mT and BpT ligand complexes (see the SI) lead to similar results, with free energy differences of only up to 3-4 kcal/mol. In a final step, intermediate $[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}_s)(\text{O}_2\text{H})]^+$ can release a hydroperoxo radical and generate $^2[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{DpT})_2]^+$ *via* re-coordination of the S centre of the DpT ligand. Similarly to $^3\text{TS1}$ (see Figure 4), the transition state for this transformation ($^3\text{TS3}$, +38.4 kcal/mol) can be described as seven-coordinate structure with $\text{Fe}\cdots\text{O}$ and $\text{Fe}\cdots\text{S}$ distances of 2.38 and 2.68 Å, respectively.

Comentado [D9]: Creo que es eliminable, la lia y no lleva a nada....

Comentado [D10]: 2 o 3

Comentado [D11]: 5 no?

Comentado [D12]: Habra que poner algo de que el Relay del proton del SCNHN al NH es "feasible"???

Fi

Figure 5. Computational (DFT) results on the oxidation of $^3[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{\text{MH}})_2\text{O}_2]^+$. Values in italics correspond to free energies in kcal/mol, quoted relative to $[\text{Fe}(\text{DpT})(\text{DpT}^{\text{SCNHN}})]^+$ and O_2 , distances in Å.

Comentado [D13]: Sin singulete, Renombar TS ???

As noted above, these computational results are relatively similar for the three studied complexes. However, the corresponding thermal and pressure activation parameters included in Table 1,⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸

and derived from the dependence of the values of ${}^0k_{\text{ox}}$ and ${}^Hk_{\text{ox}}$ with temperature and pressure (see above stoichiometry effects), show clear differences between the two types of ligands used (BpT and DpT *versus* Dp44mT), even for the common ${}^Hk_{\text{ox}}$ path. This is, evidently, a result of the employed level of theory not being able to feature such effects. Experimentally, while the coordination environment of the iron centres is not expected to change much on oxidation (the crystal structure data are very similar for both ferrous and ferric complexes of the family),^{24,54} the oxygen to superoxide reduction and its charge increase is expected to produce much more important solvational changes. These will be very relevant for the network of hydrogen bonds with surrounding solvent molecules, including the dangling $-\text{NH}_2$ or $-\text{NMe}_2$ units and any charge created throughout the dechelation process of the ligand. **At this point it is important to note the limitations of current state-of-the-art DFT methodology to reproduce the experimental solvational changes and entropy values.**

Comentado [M14]: Jeremy N. Harvey, Fahmi Himo, Feliu Maseras, and Lionel Perrin, ACS Catal. 2019, 9, 6803–6813.

Adding up, for the complexes with ligands with unsubstituted ($-\text{NH}_2$) amine groups (DpT and BpT), the values of the activation entropies for the spontaneous path are close to zero, indicating that any ordering on going to the transition state from the possible steady-state intermediate indicated in Scheme 3 (left) is compensated. The values are less negative than those found in MeOH solution, in agreement with a desolvation to reach the transition state. For the acid-catalysed path for the same complexes, the values of ΔH^\ddagger are smaller and those for ΔS^\ddagger more negative, which suggest the formation of a stronger and more complex hydrogen-bonded network facilitating the electron transfer from the more charged intermediate indicated in Scheme 3 (R = H, right).

Scheme 3

For the Dp44mT system, the values of the enthalpy and entropy of activation are dramatically different from those for the -NH₂ containing complexes. Given the fact that no spontaneous path is observed, reaction from the intermediate suggested in Scheme 3 (left) is not occurring. For the acid catalysed path, the need of the protonation of the central $\cdots\text{S-C-N-N}\cdots$ nitrogen (and its relay to the terminal amine group, Scheme 3, R = Me, right) in the proposed intermediate makes the transition state enthalpically less favourable, and produces an important entropy increase due to the desolvation of the aqueous protons needed.

In view of the relevant information that can be extracted from the ΔV^\ddagger data, the activation volumes for the DpT and Dp44mT ligand systems were determined at pH = 5.0 (where the limiting value $^Hk_{\text{ox}}$ in Equation 1 is already reached and $\Delta V^\ddagger = \Delta V^\ddagger_{\text{H}}$) and at pH = 8.0 (where the value of k_{ox} in Equation 1 is *ca.* $^0k_{\text{ox}}$ and $\Delta V^\ddagger = \Delta V^\ddagger_0$). Table 1 and Figure 6 collect the data derived under these conditions. Again, for the common $\Delta V^\ddagger_{\text{H}}$ parameter the values are especially diverse, in agreement with the radical difference in polarity and hydrogen-bonding capability between the dangling terminal amino groups of the two ligands. For the Dp44mT complex, the increase in entropy on going to the transition state is accompanied by an increase in the volume ($+8.2 \pm 0.5 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), which has to be related to the desolvation of aqueous protons (see above) and formation of the expanded hydrogen-bonded network. For the DpT ligand complex the value determined for $\Delta V^\ddagger_{\text{H}}$ is negative ($-12 \pm 1 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicating a compression on going to the transition state with practically no increase on ordering (ΔS^\ddagger slightly negative) in good agreement with a partial destruction of a large hydrogen bonding network.

Figure 6.- $\ln(k_{\text{ox}})$ versus P plot for the systems studied in aqueous solution at 10 °C.

As for the value of ΔV^{\ddagger}_0 for the DpT complex (the only one measured for the spontaneous, $^0k_{\text{ox}}$, redox step) the much closer to zero value than that for the $^{\text{H}}k_{\text{ox}}$ path, which agrees with a behaviour of the non-protonated $-\text{NH}_2$ units midway between the two situations indicated above with no extra positive charges involved.

Reactions with hydrogen peroxide

UV-Vis time-resolved experiments for the oxidation of the complexes with hydrogen peroxide in aqueous solutions indicated the presence of photochemical activity leading to unexpected products. That is, the results have been found to be dependent on the illumination/monitoring wavelength range, light intensity, and integration time of the signal when monitoring (Figure 7).⁵⁹

Figure 7.- Absorbance/time changes (registered with full white illumination) occurring on a 0.1 mM solution of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{Dp44mT})_2]$ and 3.63 mM H_2O_2 . The inset corresponds to the comparison of the final spectra obtained, with that of the Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} thiosemicarbazone complexes ($\text{pH} = 7.3$, 25°C).

As a whole, the disappearance of the MLCT (*ca.* 620 nm) band (signalling an Fe^{II} complex) occurs much faster than for the reaction with dioxygen, in agreement with the lack of H_2O_2 in the final reaction mixtures indicated above. A final spectrum with a peak at *ca.* 550 nm (Figure 7, inset) has also been detected on white illumination of Fe^{III} complex solutions in the presence of hydrogen peroxide. This fact indicates a reactivity that could be related either to a ligand oxidation or to a photochemical process occurring on the ferric species initially formed, or both. UV-Vis monitoring of solutions with added hydrogen peroxide of the free thiosemicarbazone ligands produced dramatic changes (Figure S1) leading to semicarbazone ligands, as indicated by mass spectrometry, thus

validating the first possibility. However, reducing illumination to the 500-800 nm range, simplified the reaction pattern in Figure 7, thus agreeing with the existence of some concurrent process involved in the full reaction process. **At this point, it should be noted that a variety of oxidation and desulfurization processes has been observed for related thiosemicarbazones and their complexes under a variety of conditions, although a detailed mechanistic description is still pending.**

Electrochemical experiments conducted on more concentrated samples of the $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{DpT})_2]^+$ complex (1 mM in 70/30 MeCN/H₂O to insure solubility, no buffer, $[\text{Fe}]:[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] = 10:1$) indicate the presence of three different iron species under white-illuminated reaction conditions (Figure 8). The signal of the expected $\text{Fe}^{\text{III/II}}$ *bis*-TSC complex pair is observed, but a new quasi-reversible ($\Delta E = 100$ mV) signal appears at *ca.* -270 mV, which is associated with a putative $\text{Fe}^{\text{III/II}}$ semicarbazone pair produced by oxidation of the ligand, in agreement with that observed for similar semicarbazone Fe^{III} complexes already studied.⁶⁰ A further irreversible signal at *ca.* -470 mV is also evident in the reaction mixture. On increasing the concentration of H₂O₂ the signal due to the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III/II}}$ *bis*-DpT pair becomes less dominant, while that at -270 increases its relative intensity (Figure S2). On long standing under 200-800 nm white illumination only the more negative, irreversible, signal is observed. It seems clear that, in parallel to the oxidation with hydrogen peroxide of the iron centre of the $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{DpT})_2]$, a thiosemicarbazone to semicarbazone ligand desulfurization also takes place. The final putative semicarbazone Fe^{III} complex does not seem to be stable photochemically in aqueous solution and a process leading to a new compound is observed (as indicated by the UV-Vis monitoring). **Further reactivity of such complexes and ligands has been established for similar systems.⁶¹** In this respect when the electrochemical experiments indicated above are conducted in the dark only the signals due to the thiosemicarbazone and carbazone $\text{Fe}^{\text{III/II}}$ pairs are observed (Figure S2).

Comentado [M15]: Además de la ref 61 actual:

Rosa Pedrido, María J. Romero, Manuel R. Bermejo, Ana M. González-Noya, Iria García-Lema, and Guillermo Zaragoza, *Chem. Eur. J.* 2008, 14, 500 – 512

Rosa Pedrido, María J. Romero, Manuel R. Bermejo, Miguel Martínez-Calvo, Ana M. González-Noya and Guillermo Zaragoza, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 8329–8340

Alfonso Castiñeiras and Rosa Pedrido, *Dalton Trans.*, 2010, 39, 3572–3584

Patricia Gomez-Saiz, Javier Garcia-Tojal, Virginia Diez-Gomez, Ruben Gil-Garcia, Jose Luis Pizarro, Maria Isabel Arriortua, Teofilo Rojo, *Inorganic Chemistry Communications* 8 (2005) 259–262

Comentado [M16]: Yo quitaría esta frase si se pone la que he incluido más arriba

Figure 8.- Cyclic voltammetry of a 1 mM solution of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{DpT})_2]$ after reaction with 0.1 mM of H_2O_2 under white illumination conditions (electrochemical experiment conditions stated in the Experimental).

In agreement with the complexities indicated above, the spectral changes observed for the reaction are strongly dependent on the illumination conditions, hindering a detailed kinetic study. To reduce the impact of any photochemical processes, experiments were conducted with illumination limited to the 500-800 nm range and the values of the initial rates produced data that depend both on pH and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$ (Figure S3). While the partial order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$ is 0.5 for DpT and BpT and of 1.0 for Dp44mT complexes, the order of the rate with respect to $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$ is 1.0 for DpT and BpT and 0.5 for Dp44mT derivatives. This fact indicates, again, the importance of the interaction with the -NH₂ groups in the reactivity. Given the complex concentration dependence and the photochemical behaviour, no further studies were conducted on this subject.

Conclusions

The oxidation reaction of *bis*-thiosemicarbazone complexes of Fe^{II} with oxygen has been studied kinetic-mechanistically and very different behaviours have been observed depending on the -NH₂ or -NMe₂ nature (DpT and BpT *versus* Dp44mT) of the dangling amino group on the TSC ligands. While an acid assisted reaction path operates for all the systems, involving a protonated intermediate, the acid-independent pathway only operates for the complexes with dangling -NH units in the TSC ligands. The data obtained do not correlate with the redox potential of the complexes, thus indicating that the outer-sphere mechanism found in methanol solution does not operate under the present conditions. DFT calculations indicate that the formation of a seven-coordinate intermediate containing two TSC ligands plus the oxidising O₂ molecule is disfavoured. Contrarily, the formation of a six-coordinate intermediate in steady-state conditions *via* the cleavage of a Fe-S bond and coordination of the O₂ molecule is energetically feasible. From this point, and in the absence of added protons, the reaction is likely to be assisted by the dangling -NH groups of the dechelated TSC ligand, which does not allow for the reaction to occur for the Dp44mT ligand system. In the presence of added acid, protonation of the central N in the $\cdots\text{S-C-N-N}\cdots$ chelate unit allows for a proton assistance of the reaction *via* its relay to the dangling amine groups, even for the

fully substituted Dp44mT system. Results thus add further relevance to the nature of the spectator sites of the ligands in biologically important processes such as the formation of ROS in oxygen centred reactions. In addition, the results of DFT calculations suggest the possibility of formation under steady state conditions of Fe^{III} superoxo and hydroperoxo intermediates similar to those observed for P450 and related enzymes and model complexes.

The reaction of the same Fe^{II} bis-thiosemicarbazone complexes with H₂O₂ has been found to be more than one order of magnitude faster, occurring in parallel with a series of processes that involve desulfurization of the thiosemicarbazone ligands to produce semicarbazone iron species. Furthermore, the actuation of a series of photochemical reactions occurring on the Fe^{III} species has also been detected and found to be non-operative under reduced 500-800 nm illumination.

Comentado [M17]: See for example:

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